

Evaluation of the Implementation Marketing Mix and Relationship with Business Development

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Abstract:- The importance of the role of business is one of the factors that must be considered by the government in maintaining economic stability and as a development plan in the future. The government directly has an important role in business development which can be done by implementing economic policies in an effort to maintain the national economy. As a form of contribution by business actors in supporting economic policies, it is necessary to have the independence of business actors in formulating business development strategies. This study aims to find out how the marketing mix is implemented for business development as well as conduct an in-depth evaluation of the marketing mix application so that it can be known with certainty about its impact on business development.

Based on the results of the research described earlier, it can be concluded that the DPR Putra business has implemented the 7P marketing mix strategy, namely product, price, place, promotion, people, physical evidence and process. The evaluation results show that product, price, place, promotion, people, physical evidence and process must be carried out properly because they are closely related to business operations. In addition, this study found that the implementation of the marketing mix by business actors had a very good impact on business development. This is indicated by the existence of good service from business actors, promotions carried out using social media properly so as to be able to increase the turnover of business actors which can be measured by the amount of income that continues to increase, but the obstacles found according to researchers are in certain conditions of purchase consumers experienced a slight decline. This is due to weather factors and also national holidays which result in many consumers not being in the work environment. This can be explained that most consumers of DPR PUTRA business actors are consumers who work or carry out daily activities.

Keywords:- *marketing mix 7P; business development.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) have an important and strategic role in national economic development. The important role seen from the contribution of MSMEs in having an impact on increasing economic growth, reducing unemployment through continuous employment and distribution of development results[1]. Empirically, MSMEs are also manifested by not being affected by the monetary crisis. The crisis that hit Indonesia in the 1997-1998 period showed the ability of MSMEs to survive and survive well[2]. In principle, MSMEs are an important component in the economy of a region[3]. MSMEs have a big role in economic development. To maintain the survival of MSMEs in the midst of current business competition, an appropriate marketing strategy management is needed to achieve company goals[4].

These problems provide awareness for the government in implementing policies related to business stability and sustainability. Economic policies that are able to support business development have a good impact on public trust in the government so that indirectly there must be reciprocity for business actors in supporting economy policies[5]. As concrete evidence that business actors in an effort to support government economic policies can be implemented through the independence of business actors in carrying out business development strategies[6]. The existence of COVID-19 has caused SMEs to experience a decrease in sales. In order to be able to maintain their business in the conditions of COVID-19, business actors need a strategy to help market their products even though sales are not as high as before COVID-19[7].

The implementation of business development strategies carried out by business actors can be done in several ways, including by implementing a marketing mix[8]. Marketing mix as an appropriate marketing strategy, marketing mix can be done by using four components, namely price product promotion and place[9]. However, seeing the problems in business actors, it is not certain that the 4P marketing mix can be implemented properly[10]. This requires business actors to develop a more effective strategy, namely by using the strategy of implementing the 7P marketing mix as an evaluation step for business actors in implementing the marketing mix. It is necessary to measure success indicators including measuring that the implementation can be carried out as well as a basic evaluation in carrying out the marketing mix strategy[11].

This research was conducted at one of the businesses in Bojonegoro Regency, East Java Province with the business name DPR PUTRA, this business experienced problems in the aspect of human resources in utilizing technology and had experienced a significant decrease in turnover during the COVID-19 Pandemic. However, it does not have an impact on the losses of the business being run. With good management control by business actors, the DPR PUTRA business has survived to this day. One of the strategies carried out by business actors is to implement a marketing mix.

Price is one of the considerations felt by consumers in making purchases of products[12]. Purchasing decisions, consumers will think that the money spent on a product must be in accordance with the level of consumer satisfaction felt[13]. Price is also the main comparison and is very influential in consumer decision making in purchasing products or services[14]. Consumers will compare the price with the quality obtained and compare with other similar products or services, in this case it can be explained that lower prices and the quality of the products obtained are in accordance with the wishes of consumers, it will have an impact on purchasing decisions made by consumers[15]. Thus, consumers will feel the appropriate level of satisfaction with the product or service in accordance with the wishes of consumers[16]. Based on the results of observations made in this study, it was found that price is the main consideration in influencing consumers to purchase products for businesses, so that the marketing mix component on the price aspect applied by businesses is able to influence consumer purchasing decisions for products.

Promotion is one aspect of supporting business development, promotion is positioned as an alternative to introducing products or services to consumers[17]. Thus, it can be identified that companies must utilize and implement promotional strategies in an effort to introduce products or services to consumers very carefully. Companies must think about good promotion strategies that can be carried out by companies, think about implementing promotions according to market share and market segmentation for products and services provided by business actors[18]. In this case the extent to which consumers know the quality of products and services that they feel will go through the promotion stage so that promotions must be carried out properly by business actors because they give the impression of products and services that are felt by consumers[19]. Appropriate promotions will be easily accepted by consumers, but promotions that are not appropriate will have an impact on the high costs that must be borne by businesses[20]. Basically the level of company efficiency is very much a consideration in decision making, especially in the decision to carry out a promotion strategy[21].

Product is one of the strengths for a company, but it is also a weakness for the company too[22]. In this case the product becomes one of the main alternatives to give an impression and response to the company[23]. Thus the product is one of the core strategies to be carried out and

introduced to consumers by the company[24]. Companies need to carry out and determine marketing strategies that are suitable for consumers, one of which is by introducing products to consumers[25]. Improving product quality through product differentiation and diversification needs to be done[26]. Differentiation is carried out with the aim of providing information to consumers that the products created by the company have very good characteristics or differences compared to competing products[27]. While product diversification needs to be carried out by companies with the aim of providing information and increasing market share so that consumers will have all their needs met through one company[28]. Thus the company must prioritize quality improvement through product differentiation and product development through diversification. Steps to improve quality through differentiation and diversification are a strategy for the company to further develop and increase the productivity of business operations[29].

Place is one of the alternatives that is taken into account for the company[30]. The element of place is said to be good if there is easy access for potential customers and provides appropriate reciprocal relationships with the company so that the continuity of transactions carried out by customers and the company runs continuously[31]. Place has an important role in helping companies to ensure their products[32]. Places or distribution channels are various activities carried out by the company in order to make the company's products easy to obtain and available to target customers[33]. While the purpose of determining the location is to provide goods or services needed and desired by consumers at the right time and place[34]. Place is one of the main priorities in the marketing strategy as a distribution channel that brings together companies and individuals and takes over rights or assists in the transfer of rights to certain goods or services, namely as long as the goods or services pass from the hands of producers to consumers[35].

Physical evidence is the main concern for consumers and encourages repurchasing interest in products or services[36]. Physical evidence will determine the close relationship between the company and consumers so that it needs to be considered properly[37]. Physical evidence is able to provide good and bad perceptions to consumers, if the company has good and attractive physical evidence in accordance with the minimum desires of consumers for the company, it will have a good impact on consumers[38]. If the physical evidence provided by the company to consumers is bad and does not match what consumers expect, it will have a negative impact on the company[39]. Thus, physical evidence must be able to be realized and provided by the company. Physical evidence can be used to achieve the goals and objectives of a business by developing a sustainable competitive advantage in the specified target market[40].

Process is one of the influential factors in the marketing mix, especially in the form of services[41]. This is because service consumers, in the fulfillment process, are also actively involved as part of the service itself[42].

Process is defined as a procedure in a series of activities to deliver services from producers to consumers[43]. In the context of services or services provided to consumers, processes are procedures carried out by companies that support the implementation of the process of resource activities in order to form the desired product or service[44]. Processes can have an impact on natural satisfaction that arises from consumers to companies, in this case aspects of the process will be of particular concern in efforts to create products and services[45].

People are people or human resources. People are all actors who play a role in the presentation of services so that they can influence buyer perceptions[46]. The elements of people are company employees, consumers, and other consumers in service-related environments[47]. All attitudes and actions of employees and employee appearance have an influence on consumer perceptions or the successful delivery of products or services[48]. The people in a company are the people who are involved in the production process and finalizing the product until it reaches the consumer[49]. These human resources are very important, and even become the spearhead in the process of providing services, to consumers or customers of the products or services created by the company[50]. The importance of human resources in this case will encourage the formation of a culture that is good and acceptable to consumers so that people, in this case, need to be constantly improved in order to maintain consumer confidence in the company's products and services[51].

This research has a focus on evaluating the marketing mix carried out by business actors and analyzing its application in an effort to improve business development. The marketing mix that will later be used in services is a set of tactical and controlled marketing tools that are integrated by the company to produce the response the target market wants[52]. Today's service marketing is no longer limited to the 4P Marketing Mix, but a Marketing Mix that is more than 4P, namely the 7P marketing mix[53].

The marketing mix consists of all the things a company can do to influence the demand for its product[54]. These various possibilities can be grouped into seven aspects, which include: product, price, place, promotion, people, physical evidence, and process[55]. In the midst of increasingly fierce competition, companies must be smarter in determining strategies to market their products to the public[56]. Some of the expected impacts if MSMEs implement the 7P marketing mix strategy include sales growth, capital growth, workforce growth and market growth[57].

Several previous studies explained that by using the Marketing Mix 7P method, it was found that the accuracy level of the marketing strategy formulation system was very high. Thus the Marketing Strategy that has been made is of sufficient standard and can be used as a marketing analysis instrument[58]. The marketing approach has developed an important tool, namely the marketing mix[42]. Furthermore, in the marketing mix, it is known as

7P as the most appropriate marketing tool as an approach to consumers, because the classic 4P marketing mix is not efficient enough to drive an organization. The latest research conducted is to identify qualitatively in evaluating the application of the 7P marketing mix to MSMEs and at the same time to find out the impact of implementing the 7P marketing mix on MSME business development. determining recency, namely analyzing SMEs because the SMEs selected in this study are types of businesses whose activities are to produce and sell both products and services in the aspect of direct distribution channels.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Marketing Mix 7P

The marketing mix is the controllable set of tactical marketing tools that the company blends to produce the response it wants in the target market. There are 7 factors in the marketing mix strategy[52].

- Products can be defined as anything that is offered to the market in order to satisfy the wants or needs of consumers. The success of a company's product in the eyes of consumers is if the product is able to provide satisfaction to customers, then the company will be seen and considered successful. And if the resulting product is not able to meet customer desires, then the company is considered a failure. Because of that we need a quality product. Product quality is the ability of an item to provide appropriate results or performance even beyond what the customer wants, such as an attractive design, a different brand from other products (unique), and the shape of the packaging of the product is able to attract consumers. In addition, the product packaging produced is not only related to the product model, but good quality packaging will be able to increase product durability longer.
- Price can be defined as an amount of money that has an exchange value and is used in order to gain profit by owning or using a product or service. There are four indicators that characterize price, namely price affordability, price competitiveness, price compatibility with product quality, and price compatibility with benefits. Another important marketing element is the price which is the amount that must be paid by consumers to get a product. The definition of price is an exchange rate that can be equated with money or other goods for the benefits derived from an item or service for a person or group at a certain time and a certain place. Price is the strength of the exchange rate of goods and services that can increase sales volume and company profits. Price is an amount of money as a medium of exchange to obtain a product or service. Price can also be said to determine the value of a product in the minds of consumers. More about price, that price is the only element of the marketing mix that generates revenue. The other elements incur costs. Price is also one of the most flexible elements of the marketing mix. Prices can be changed on the fly, unlike product characteristics and distribution agreements.
- Place means relating to where the service/product company must be headquartered and carry out its activities. In marketing books, place is usually translated

as marketing channel. According to Kotler, a marketing channel is a series of interdependent organizations that are not involved in the process of making a product or service ready for use or consumption. A strategic location, comfortable and easy to reach will be the main attraction for customers. Location selection is the most expensive investment value, because location can be said to determine whether or not visitors are busy. Place has an important role in helping companies to ensure their products. Places or distribution channels are various activities carried out by the company in order to make the company's products easy to obtain and available to target customers. While the purpose of determining the location is to provide goods or services needed and desired by consumers at the right time and place. Distribution channels as a collection of companies and individuals who take over rights or assist in the transfer of rights to certain goods or services, namely as long as the goods or services pass from the hands of producers to consumers.

- Promotion is a company activity in communicating the sale of its products in the market and dealing directly with the public. Promotion is one of the most important marketing mix variables for opening new market shares or expanding marketing networks. Promotion is a marketing activity that seeks to disseminate information, influence or remind the target market (consumers) of the company and its products so that they are willing to accept, buy and be loyal to the products offered by the company concerned. Promotion is also one of the determining factors for the success of marketing programs. No matter how good the quality of a product is, if consumers have never heard of it and are not sure that the product will be useful for them, then they will never buy it. That's why the purpose of promotion is to provide information and convince consumers of the benefits of these products. Promotion is a communication of information between sellers and buyers that aims to change the attitudes and behavior of buyers, who previously did not know to become familiar, so that they become buyers and still remember the product.
- People are all people/actors involved in the process of delivering services to consumers and influencing consumer perceptions, for example service provider personnel, customers and other customers related to the service. From the above understanding, it can be understood that people are all actors who play a role in providing services so that they can influence buyer perceptions. The elements of people are company employees, consumers, and other consumers in the service environment. All attitudes and actions of employees and employee appearance have an influence on consumer perceptions or the success of service delivery. The important role of people is in providing quality service to customers.
- Physical evidence is the physical environment where services are created, which directly interact with consumers. In the marketing mix, there are two kinds of physical evidence, namely, the first is the design and layout of buildings such as classes, school buildings,

libraries, sports fields and others. Second, supporting evidence, namely added value which if it stands alone will not play any role, such as report cards, student records and others. Physical facilities are important components that also influence consumer decisions to buy and use products/services. Physical evidence is a supporting facility and is part of service marketing which has an important role. This will further strengthen the existence of these services because services delivered to customers or consumers usually require supporting facilities in their delivery. With the existence of physical supporting facilities, the service is expected to be easily understood by customers. Providing added value from goods or service providers to consumers can be in the form of physical evidence. Physical evidence of goods or services is a tangible form that the manufacturer offers to customers or potential customers.

- Process is a procedure, mechanism, and a series of activities to deliver services from producers to consumers. the process is one of the influential factors in marketing, especially in the form of services. This is because the customer is also actively involved as part of the service itself. Process is defined as a procedure in a series of activities to deliver services from producers to consumers/consumers of services, in the process of fulfilling them. The process is a real procedure, a mechanism, as well as the flow of activities that are conveyed and is a presentation system for the company's service operations. All existing work activities constitute a process, and the process involves procedures, activities, tasks, schedules, mechanisms, and routines in which goods or services are distributed to customers.

B. Business Development

In global competition, companies are expected to be able to provide more added value to the goods/services offered either in quality (better) or efficiently (more efficient) than competitors[59]. This is specifically difficult for MSMEs to do, due to the lack of management skills and limited working capital management[60]. Despite these limitations, MSMEs tend to have resilience (stable performance) to changes in the business and economic climate[61].

Performance refers to the level of achievement of the company within a certain period. Performance in the company can be seen from the company's sales level, margin level, return on capital, turnover rate and market share achieved[62]. Performance is a series of various management activities that provide an overview of the extent to which the results of activities that have been achieved in carrying out their duties and responsibilities in public accountability in the form of progress, success or deficiencies that occur[63].

Business continuity in MSMEs can be seen from the company's success in innovating, managing employees and customers and returning their initial capital[64]. Where this shows that the company has an orientation to develop and sees opportunities for innovation on an ongoing basis[65]. With easy measurement (through perception) it is expected to be able to show the actual

conditions of these MSMEs, which can be done by calculating the performance of MSMEs with easy indicators of economic growth and increasing total income[59].

Business success is a situation where the business has increased from previous results and has become the main part of a company where all activities in it are aimed at achieving success[66]. Entrepreneurial success or failure is influenced by various factors both external and internal. Influential internal factors include the will, abilities and weaknesses that exist in oneself. As for the external factors are opportunities and opportunities for the business occupied[67].

Entrepreneurship is determined by achievement motives, optimism, value attitudes, and entrepreneurial status or success[68]. People who are successful in entrepreneurship are people who can combine values, main traits (attitude patterns), and behavior with the provision of knowledge, experience, and practical skills[69]. Business success is the state that the business has improved from its previous results. Business success is the ultimate goal of a company, that all activities in it are intended to achieve success[70]. Entrepreneurial success is not synonymous with how successful a person is in accumulating money or assets and becoming rich, because wealth can be obtained in various ways so as to generate added value[71].

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This research was conducted using qualitative methods and with a descriptive quantitative analysis approach through a triangulation model. The choice of a descriptive quantitative analysis research approach through the triangulation model was determined by the researcher as an update to the model of previous studies which was measured using quantitative analysis. It is hoped that research using a descriptive quantitative analysis approach through the triangulation model will be able to measure the implementation of the 7P marketing mix properly and provide recommendations for research results based on the impacts that arise.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Following are the results of data analysis to determine the effect of brand image, promotion, service quality and trust on purchasing decisions. Following are the results of data analysis through validity tests:

A. Evaluation of Marketing Mix Implementation

The application of the 7P marketing mix is carried out by business actors with the aim of being able to increase competition in their business field, this indicates that companies or MSMEs can implement this strategy so that business development can be ensured properly. The following is the result of an analysis of the implementation of the 7P marketing mix by the DPR Putra.

a) Product

Products can be defined as anything that is offered to the market in order to satisfy the wants or needs of consumers. The success of a company's product in the eyes of consumers is if the product is able to provide satisfaction to customers, then the company will be seen and considered successful. And if the resulting product is not able to meet customer desires, then the company is considered a failure therefore we need a quality product.

Product quality is the ability of an item to provide appropriate results or performance even beyond what the customer wants, such as an attractive design, a different brand from other products (unique), and the shape of the packaging of the product is able to attract consumers. In addition, the product packaging produced is not only related to the product model, but good quality packaging will be able to increase product durability longer.

One of the things that needs to be improved is the application of the 7P marketing mix, products, products are goods that will be offered to consumers to fulfill their wants and needs. So that the quality and taste of a product must really be maintained by a business actor to attract consumer interest. The products offered by this business are very interesting and have unique characteristics as well as innovations made by business actors whose main ingredients are agricultural products by combining the concept of a restaurant. Meeting consumer needs is a reflection of the products presented. Creating creative and innovative products so as to innovate ready-to-eat food products so that they are more in demand by the public is the main focus. With this innovation, businesses can open up new market opportunities because they can provide something that attracts consumer interest.

Based on the results of the interviews, it can be concluded that the implementation of the marketing mix strategy on product aspects is a strong reason to attract consumer attention so that consumers are able to repurchase the products they have purchased. Based on the results of interviews conducted with business actors who also explained the success of business actors in implementing the marketing mix strategy on product aspects, it was concluded that implementing the marketing mix strategy on product aspects was one of the successes that could be realized by business actors, business actors were able to maintain their products and can innovate products with the aim that products can be recognized and accepted by the general public without leaving old products or initial products, in choosing a product, always try to maintain the quality of its products always emphasizes its employees to always maintain product cleanliness, namely by cleaning the equipment used use one

daily, and pay attention to the expiration time of raw materials.

Thus, based on the results of the analysis, it can be formulated the results of evaluating the implementation of the marketing mix that has been implemented by business actors based on one aspect, namely the product. It can be concluded that the product aspect of the implementation of the marketing mix must be carried out so that it will have an impact on business success.

b) Price

Price is the strength of the exchange rate of goods and services that can increase sales volume and company profits. Price is an amount of money as a medium of exchange to obtain a product or service. Price can also be said to determine the value of a product in the minds of consumers. More about price, that price is the only element of the marketing mix that generates revenue. The other elements incur costs. Price is also one of the most flexible elements of the marketing mix. Prices can be changed on the fly, unlike product characteristics and distribution agreements.

The pricing process must be well structured in order to provide benefits for the business being run. Price is the only marketing mix instrument that can provide direct revenue. Although other instruments also play a role in generating income, costs are required to realize it. Prices must be prepared properly, because mistakes in determining prices will have an impact on business trips. Setting a price that is too high has the potential to lose the market, while setting a low price has the potential to incur a loss. Introducing attractive price offers can be done by businesses. The important role of price in retaining and finding customers is needed for the success of DPR Putra business.

Based on the results of interviews conducted by business actors, it can be explained that price fixing is carried out by business actors with the principles of transparency and prudence. This is because the business is its own business so that the profits earned are not shared with other parties. The understanding that business actors define business profits above all else will have an impact on activities that should be customer oriented and change the essence of the core business activities themselves.

Based on observations and the results of interviews conducted by researchers, it can be concluded that the pricing strategy in implementing this marketing mix is very profitable for DPR Putra business actors, the reason being that production costs are cheaper because the raw materials come directly from the plants themselves. The purpose of applying an appropriate price is to satisfy and attract consumers' attention to the product of interest,

pricing is done on the basis of obtaining an appropriate profit level and according to consumers the price is cheap so that consumers are always willing to buy it repeatedly. however, the obstacle in setting prices is that business actors must consider the level of profit and price competition with the same product by other business actors, this is because competitive pricing is very difficult to implement and must have price consistency (prices do not change quickly).

Thus, based on the results of the analysis, it can be formulated the results of evaluating the implementation of the marketing mix that has been implemented by business actors based on one aspect, namely price. It can be concluded that the price aspect of the marketing mix implementation must be carried out so that it will have an impact on business success.

c) Place

The ability of business actors to shorten distribution channels and make it easier for products to be found is of concern to consumers. A marketing channel is a set of interdependent organizations that are not involved in the process of making a product or service ready for use or consumption. A strategic location, comfortable and easy to reach will be the main attraction for customers. Location selection is the most expensive investment value, because location can be said to determine whether or not visitors are busy. Place has an important role in helping companies to ensure their products. Places or distribution channels are various activities carried out by the company in order to make the company's products easy to obtain and available to target customers. The importance of determining the location is one of the strategies that must be carried out by business actors in dealing with the impossibility that occurs regarding business success, so that the place of business becomes one of the alternative choices made in facing competition.

Based on the interviews, it can be concluded that the place is the location where a business markets or produces products that will later be marketed to consumers. Determining the location also affects whether or not the production and marketing activities of a business run smoothly. In this study, the DPR Putra business area is located in Bogo Village, Kapas District, Bojonegoro Regency. Even though it is located in a village, this business location is easily accessible and reachable by visitors. In addition, many outside activities are carried out in the village because it is known as a culinary village and a tourist village in Bojonegoro Regency. The results of this study also indicate that the location owned by business actors is very strategic, namely it is located on the left side of the road, so that as soon as a village visitor enters, they

will see the place and the attractive design of the place.

Thus, based on the results of the analysis, it can be formulated the results of evaluating the implementation of the marketing mix that has been implemented by business actors based on one aspect, namely place, it can be concluded that the aspect of place in the implementation of the marketing mix must be carried out so that it will have an impact on business success.

d) Promotion

Promotion is a marketing activity that seeks to disseminate information, influence/persuade or remind the target market (consumers) of the company and its products to be willing to accept, buy and be loyal to the products offered by the company concerned. Promotion is also one of the determining factors for the success of marketing programs. No matter how good the quality of a product is, if consumers have never heard of it and are not sure that the product will be useful for them, then they will never buy it. Promotion is one of the alternatives carried out by business actors in increasing sales so that in supporting the success of managed businesses it is necessary to increase and have a good marketing strategy by business actors, this will support effective and efficient business operations and be able to expedite distribution channels properly (right on target).

Based on the results of the interviews, it can be explained that the promotion strategy carried out by business actors in several ways, including through social media such as Facebook, WhatsApp stories and other media that support and are controlled by business actors. Determining this strategy is very effective to do, besides that business actors also approach prospective customers directly so that there is good communication between sellers and buyers. Thus, business actors can take advantage of technological advances, bearing in mind that developments in information technology make it easier for business actors to reach consumers more quickly, easily and cheaply.

Based on the results of the interviews, it can be explained that the problems that occur when business actors carry out promotions are inconsistent when promoting through social media due to other activities outside of business operations, but in anticipation of this, business actors carry out promotions directly by word of mouth to several groups including official groups around their area and the MSME community, this strategy was carried out well so that it was very effective which can be proven by the existence of several official meetings and MSME events held at the place of business actors, this has become one of the strategies as well as an opportunity for business

actors business in an effort to develop the business so as to achieve the expected business success.

Thus, based on the results of the analysis, it can be formulated the results of evaluating the implementation of the marketing mix that has been implemented by business actors based on one aspect, namely promotion, it can be concluded that the promotion aspect of the marketing mix implementation must be carried out so that it will have an impact on business success.

e) People

This instrument focuses on the ability and quality of product providers to influence consumers. The focus of sustainable business is not only on products, but also pays attention to the competence of human resources. The ability of human resources in solving problems needs to be improved. Human resources are one of the valuable assets in an organization, they must be cared for so that they have a positive impact on business continuity.

Efforts to control human resources are carried out by implementing SOP (standard operating procedures) for employees. First apply discipline to employees by arriving on time according to schedule. Second, look attractive and clean. Third, prioritizing a good personality by providing the best service to consumers. Fourth, must be sensitive to the environment, always maintain the cleanliness and tidiness of the place. Fifth, making food according to the measure and always prioritizing quality. Operational control is also necessary as a form of improving the internal quality of the business so that the business can compete healthily.

Based on the results of interviews with DPR Putra business actors, they have applied the marketing mix strategy theory, namely people. This strategy is very profitable for DPR Putra business owners because with employees, the product manufacturing process and customer service process can always be carried out optimally, thus helping to increase sales levels to achieve targeted profits.

Thus, based on the results of the analysis, it can be formulated the results of evaluating the implementation of the marketing mix that has been implemented by business actors based on one aspect, namely people. It can be concluded that the people aspect of the implementation of the marketing mix must be carried out so that it will have an impact on business success.

f) Physical Evidence

Physical evidence is a supporting facility and is part of service marketing which has an important role. This will further strengthen the existence of these services because services delivered to customers or consumers usually require supporting facilities in their delivery. With the existence of physical

supporting facilities, the service is expected to be easily understood by customers. Providing added value from goods or service providers to consumers can be in the form of physical evidence. Physical evidence of goods or services is a tangible form that producers offer to customers or potential customers. The evidence in question is physical means. Physical facilities can indirectly influence consumer purchasing decisions for the goods or services offered.

Physical evidence provides an understanding of the suitability of the seller's promise with the product received by the consumer. Various marketing activities that are able to attract consumers must be proven clearly and in accordance with previous promotional stimuli. The difference between the product promised and the product received will create obstacles in the next business trip. The evidence in question is physical means. Physical facilities can indirectly influence consumer purchasing decisions for the goods or services offered. These facilities are usually in the form of physical buildings, furniture, equipment, equipment, logos, colors, and the atmosphere of the company.

The results of observations and interviews explain that the use and determination of packaging is of great concern. The use of packaging is very important because it is used to keep products safe and maintain their quality, as well as to attract consumer interest in the products being marketed. Physical evidence on the products sold are in accordance with the pictures on the menu so that it will not disappoint consumers, business actors also always prioritize the appearance of the menu being sold, the hope is that if the menu is interesting and satisfying it will become a conversation among consumer groups so that more and more people will know this product and business, Physical evidence plays an alternative role in attracting customer interest visually which can be seen by consumers directly such as choosing paint colors that are characteristic of outlets, employee uniforms, packaging appearance, quality of communication, a comfortable environment plays an important role in convincing consumers to buy products which is offered.

Thus, based on the results of the analysis, it can be formulated the results of evaluating the implementation of the marketing mix that has been implemented by business actors based on one aspect, namely physical evidence. It can be concluded that the physical evidence aspect of the marketing mix implementation must be carried out so that it will have an impact on business success.

g) Process

Process is a real procedure, a mechanism, as well as the flow of activities that are delivered and is a presentation system for the company's service operations. All existing work activities constitute a process, and the process involves procedures, activities, tasks, schedules, mechanisms, and routines in which goods or services are distributed to customers.

The process is the journey of an activity or certain activities to achieve the goals that have been targeted effectively and efficiently. Within the scope of process marketing, it is the implementation of the procedures of a business in creating and distributing the resulting product so that it can be reached and owned by consumers. The process chosen by DPR Putra business owners or employees greatly influences product efficiency, cost flexibility and product quality, so professional action is needed, namely directed, precise, thorough and clear in providing information in accordance with existing processes regarding processed products.

Based on the results of the interviews, it can be explained that efforts to develop business and achieve business success are things that must be fought for well, the process of providing services, managing and processing products, and presenting them must be done well because good results will have a good impact on consumers and trigger the emergence of a feeling to re-purchase the product. processes that are carried out properly are one of the efforts that must be made to develop the business, processes ranging from service, manufacture to presentation are carried out properly by employees, operational processes are carried out effectively and efficiently so that they are in accordance with the wishes and tastes of customers, processing and presentation processes products are also made with care to suit consumer needs and minimize bad disappointments that occur to consumers

Thus, based on the results of the analysis, it can be formulated the results of evaluating the implementation of the marketing mix that has been implemented by business actors based on one aspect, namely process, it can be concluded that the process aspect of the implementation of the marketing mix must be carried out so that it will have an impact on business success.

B. The Relationship between Marketing Mix and Business Development

The marketing mix strategy used by the DPR Putra business was able to increase its sales volume. Even though at the beginning of the product marketing process there were obstacles to sales, namely limited information, limited capital, and limited technological knowledge to support promotional activities. But with the implementation of the marketing mix strategy that is carried out correctly and in accordance with existing

theory, in other words, these seven aspects can help and play an important role in increasing sales volume and increasing the number of customers so that they can provide benefits for the DPR Putra business.

The implementation of the 7P marketing mix strategy has a positive impact on business development, this can be demonstrated by success in making sales, business actors are able to survive well in the midst of similar business competition, business success can be marked by an increase in sales, an increase in the number of employees and expansion of locations or place of business.

Performance refers to the level of achievement of the company within a certain period. Performance in the company can be seen from the company's sales level, margin level, return on capital, turnover rate and market share achieved[62]. Performance is a series of various management activities that provide an overview of the extent to which the results of activities that have been achieved in carrying out their duties and responsibilities in public accountability in the form of progress, success or deficiencies that occur[63].

Business continuity in MSMEs can be seen from the company's success in innovating, managing employees and customers and returning their initial capital[64]. Where this shows that the company has an orientation to develop and sees opportunities for innovation on an ongoing basis[65]. With easy measurement (through perception) it is expected to be able to show the actual conditions of these MSMEs, which can be done by calculating the performance of MSMEs with easy indicators of economic growth and increasing total income[59].

Business success is a situation where the business has increased from previous results and has become the main part of a company where all activities in it are aimed at achieving success[66]. Entrepreneurial success or failure is influenced by various factors both external and internal. Influential internal factors include the will, abilities and weaknesses that exist in oneself. As for the external factors are opportunities and opportunities for the business occupied[67].

Entrepreneurship is determined by achievement motives, optimism, value attitudes, and entrepreneurial status or success[68]. People who are successful in entrepreneurship are people who can combine values, main traits (attitude patterns), and behavior with the provision of knowledge, experience, and practical skills[69]. Business success is the state that the business has improved from its previous results. Business success is the ultimate goal of a company, that all activities in it are intended to achieve success[70]. Entrepreneurial success is not synonymous with how successful a person is in accumulating money or assets and becoming rich, because wealth can be obtained in various ways so as to generate added value[71].

Thus it can be concluded that the application of the marketing mix can have an impact on business development, including increasing sales, increasing the number of employees, increasing total turnover and increasing other physical aspects.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research described earlier, it can be concluded that the DPR Putra business has implemented the 7P marketing mix strategy, namely product, price, place, promotion, people, physical evidence and process. The evaluation results show that product, price, place, promotion, people, physical evidence and process must be carried out properly because they are closely related to business operations. In addition, this study found that the implementation of the marketing mix by business actors had a very good impact on business development. This is indicated by the existence of good service from business actors, promotions carried out using social media properly so as to be able to increase the turnover of business actors which can be measured by the amount of income that continues to increase, but the obstacles found according to researchers are in certain conditions of purchase consumers experienced a slight decline. This is due to weather factors and also national holidays which result in many consumers not being in the work environment. This can be explained that most consumers of DPR PUTRA business actors are consumers who work or carry out daily activities.

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